

EVALUATION OF MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF COMPOSITE PRESSURE VESSELS USING A SEGMENT-TYPE RING BURST TEST DEVICE

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ABSTRACT

Pressure vessels, used to store liquids and gases in the aerospace and automotive industries, have been currently made using composites which have high specific strength and stiffness and large tank-to-weight capacity. To verify the stability of pressure vessel, this paper deals with the development of a new segment-type ring burst test device. The most crucial factor in designing a test fixture for a pressure vessel is applying uniform radial pressures to the specimen as in the hydro-pressure test. Therefore, to verify the uniformity of the pressure in the modified test device, the hoop stress distribution was compared between hydro-pressure and segment-type test method using FE analysis. As a crucial method to reduce the strain discrepancy of the ring specimen, the number of segments was divided into 24 pieces and PTFE sheets were utilized between the segment and the specimen. Moreover, to investigate the strain distribution and fracture behavior in the experiment, the digital image correlation (DIC) method with high speed camera and the strain gage were used. Furthermore, in order to verify the experimental result using the FE analysis, the Hashin failure criteria were introduced to simulate the fracture of the composite specimen.

1 INTRODUCTION

These days, as the regulation of fuel consumption and emission gas is strengthened in the aerospace and automotive industry, weight reduction of vehicles have been required to improve the fuel efficiency. Furthermore, it has been also required the use of new environmentally friendly fuels to reduce the emission of greenhouse gases from vehicles by reducing petroleum dependency [1]. As a leading candidate, hydrogen (H₂) which can be generated from water or any energy source is now expected as a substitute material. However, in order to store hydrogen in a vehicle, there are some problems. one is that the pressure vessel should withstand a high-pressure (30-70MPa) condition because the hydrogen needs to be compressed to meet mileage up to 500km on a single charge. the other is that it also requires weight savings to meet the fuel economy regulations [2-3]. As an alternative, composite materials which have high specific strength and stiffness were widely used for the design of pressure vessels because of the necessity of light-weight structure in addition to ensuring stability. In some references, fabricating the pressure vessel using composite materials lead to a weight reduction of 40% or more and it shows highest performance compared to the conventional metal vessel [5-6]. Because of these advantages, it is required to verify the safety of pressure vessel made of composite materials and such studies are currently in progress [7-14]. In previous studies, several test methods were introduced in order to evaluate the mechanical properties of a composite pressure vessel, however, each test fixture has some drawbacks and it needs to be improved for more reliable material property evaluation.

Conventionally, the standard test method (ASTM D2585) was used to evaluate the hoop tensile property of the full-scale filament-wound pressure vessel [7]. This test method covers the determination of the apparent tensile parameters whose are predicted on defined conditions of geometry, fabrication, and test of filament-wound pressure vessels. The test can be carried out by a hydraulic pressure test and the apparent tensile strength is derived from the netting theory by measuring the strain in the hoop direction. However, conducting the test of full-scale pressure vessels is an accurate and reliable method,

it cost a lot [6]. Therefore, some studies were progressed to test the material property of pressure vessel using a ring-type specimen.

As an alternative, a standard test method (ASTM 2290) for evaluating the apparent hoop tensile strength of a ring specimen was conducted [8]. In this test method, the ring specimen is loaded through the suggested self-aligning split disk test fixture and there is a reduced area in the specimen to cause the fracture at a specific location. However, using this test method, there may be a bending moment imposed during the test between the split disk test fixture. This moment is induced by the change in the contour of the ring specimen between the two disk sections as they separate. Consequently, the test result from this test method is an apparent tensile strength rather than a true tensile strength and show a comparatively low value [9-10]. Therefore, this test method also has defects in obtaining reliable tensile hoop stresses of the pressure vessel.

There is a newly developed test method that is capable of hydro-pressure test with ring specimens [11]. In this test method, the hoop ring test fixture was newly designed and the hydro-pressure is applied by using a rubber tube. However, due to the uneven contact between the rubber tube and the specimen, the pressure applied to the specimen also was not uniform. Moreover, because of the design limitation of the test fixture, the rubber tube is in contact first with the edge of the specimen causing undesirable early failure at the edge. Therefore, it led to the reduction of fracture strain. In order to prevent this problem, the additional material as a reinforcement is attached near the edge of the ring specimen but this may change the material properties of the ring specimen. Also, it was necessary to design the thickness and width of the reinforcement for each type of specimen by FE analysis and attach the additional reinforcement at every specimen.

To prevent these problems, another test method that is capable of pressure using metal segments was newly developed [12-13]. In this test method, the compressive load of the universal testing machine is transmitted through the segments in the radial direction of the ring specimen. But the crucial problem of this segment-type test methods was there are large discrepancy of stress and strain values because of the gap between the segments and it led to uneven stress distribution in the specimen. In these studies, the strain discrepancy was compared by FE analysis according to the number of segments, however, it was limited to 2D so the strain discrepancy along the axial direction was not considered [12]. Moreover, the relation between the applied load and the resultant pressure on the ring specimen was calculated through a simple proportional equation obtained from the experimental constant using same sized steel specimen. So, it was not possible to consider each different specimen sizes. Also, it assumed the composite ring specimen as a thin-walled cylinder ignoring composite layers so it was impossible to derive the precise strength values. Moreover, unexpected early fracture due to the structural limitation of the liner used to lubricate the specimen and segments led to the use of additional reinforcements on ring specimen same as the previous test method [13].

In order to improve these limitations and to use the segment-type ring burst test device to measure more reliable material properties in pressure vessel, in this paper, the segment-type ring burst test device is redesigned and the reliability of the test device is verified by numerical and experimental approaches.

2 THEORETICAL APPROACHES IN THE RING BURST SYSTEM

2.1 Relation of loads in the segment-type ring burst system

To derive the theoretical stress and strain values of the ring specimen, the equilibrium equation between loads under the axisymmetric condition in the ring burst system was considered. Fig. 1 shows the schematic diagram of the ring burst test device where F_1 is the applied compression load, F_2 is the resultant radial load, N , N_1 , N_2 are the normal force at each contact surface, μ_1 is the coefficient of kinetic friction between the vertical column and segments, μ_2 is the coefficient of kinetic friction between segments and bottom plate, and α is the angle between vertical column and segments, respectively.

The load F_1 is applied through the vertical column and consequently transmitted to the specimen in the F_2 direction through segments. Based on the load equilibrium equation in the total system, the vertical column system and the segment system, the load relation between F_1 and F_2 can be derived in equation (1). Finally, the internal pressure P applied to the specimen can be derived by dividing F_2 by the inner area of the ring specimen.

Fig. 1 Schematic diagram of ring burst system and relation of loads.

$$F_2 = \left\{ \frac{1 - \mu_1 \tan(\alpha)}{\mu_1 + \tan(\alpha)} - \mu_2 \right\} F_1 \quad (1)$$

2.2 Derivation of hoop stress and strain

In the case of composite materials, since each lamina must be considered, the constitutive equation of stress equilibrium in cylindrical coordinates in each layer was derived. The theoretical model was investigated to calculate the hoop stress distribution at each layer in equation (2).

$$\sigma_{\theta}^{(i)} = \left(\bar{C}_{\theta\theta}^{(i)} + \bar{C}_{\theta r}^{(i)} \right) D_1^{(i)} + \frac{\left(\bar{C}_{\theta\theta}^{(i)} - \bar{C}_{\theta r}^{(i)} \right) D_2^{(i)}}{r^2} \quad (2)$$

The i means each layer, \bar{C} is the off-axis stiffness constants, D_1 and D_2 are the integral constants which can be determined by boundary conditions, respectively. This equation was derived from the radial force equilibrium with the assumption of 3D transversely isotropy elasticity and axisymmetric thick-walled cylinder under internal pressure [14]. Using the equation (1) and (2) it was possible to derive hoop stress and strain of a ring specimen at each layer.

3 FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS

3.1 Material properties

To modify the ring burst test device, the 3D Finite element analysis (FEA) of the segment-type ring burst test device was conducted using ABAQUS 2019 (SIMULIA). A quarter axisymmetric ring burst test model with a 3D 8-node isoparametric element under linear elastic condition was utilized. The material properties of each material property are shown in Table 1 and Table 2.

T700/epoxy	ρ [kg/mm ²]	E_1 [GPa]	E_2 [GPa]	E_3 [GPa]	ν_{12}	ν_{13}	ν_{23}	G_{12} [GPa]	G_{13} [GPa]	G_{23} [GPa]
	1.54	134	8.08	8.08	0.33	0.33	0.45	5.33	5.33	2.74

Table 1 Elastic material properties of T700/epoxy.

Material type	ρ [kg/mm ²]	E [GPa]	ν
Steel	7.85	200	0.3
PTFE	2.2	0.5	0.46

Table 2 Elastic material properties of steel and PTFE.

3.2 Damage initiation criteria

The Hashin damage criteria were utilized to simulate the fracture phenomenon of ring burst specimens [15-16]. This method predicts anisotropic damage in elastic brittle materials and is primarily intended for the fiber-reinforced composite material. To simulate the fracture of the composite material, four different failure modes: fiber tension, fiber compression, matrix tension, and matrix compression was considered. As a reference point for the degradation of material stiffness, the damage initiation criteria have the following general forms.

$$\text{Fiber tension } (\hat{\sigma}_{11} \geq 0) \quad F_{ft} = \left(\frac{\hat{\sigma}_{11}}{X^T}\right)^2 + \alpha \left(\frac{\hat{\sigma}_{12}}{S^L}\right)^2 = 1 \quad (3)$$

$$\text{Fiber compression } (\hat{\sigma}_{11} < 0) \quad F_{fc} = \left(\frac{\hat{\sigma}_{11}}{X^C}\right)^2 = 1 \quad (4)$$

$$\text{Matrix tension } (\hat{\sigma}_{22} \geq 0) \quad F_{mt} = \left(\frac{\hat{\sigma}_{22}}{Y^T}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\hat{\sigma}_{12}}{S^L}\right)^2 = 1 \quad (5)$$

$$\text{Matrix compression } (\hat{\sigma}_{22} < 0) \quad F_{mc} = \left(\frac{\hat{\sigma}_{22}}{2S^T}\right)^2 \left[\left(\frac{Y^C}{2S^T}\right)^2 - 1 \right] \frac{\hat{\sigma}_{22}}{Y^T} + \left(\frac{\hat{\sigma}_{12}}{S^L}\right)^2 = 1 \quad (6)$$

From the above equations $\hat{\sigma}_{ij}$ are the effective stress tensor, X^T and X^C are the tensile and compressive strengths in the fiber direction, Y^T and Y^C are the tensile and compressive strengths in the matrix direction, S^L and S^T are the longitudinal and transverse shear strengths and α is a coefficient that determines the contribution of the shear stress to the fiber tensile initiation criterion. Based on the proposed value of this coefficient in Hashin and Rotem [7], it was set as $\alpha = 0$ and $S^T = 0.5Y^C$. The exact strength values obtained from the experiment are shown in the Table 3.

Strength	X^T	X^C	Y^T	Y^C	S^L	S^T
[MPa]	2480	44	1170	129	82.4	64.5

Table 3 Damage initiation properties of T700/epoxy.

3.3 Damage evolution law

The damage evolution law in Hashin failure criteria assumes that damage is characterized by progressive degradation of material stiffness and it leads to material failure. As a factor determining the failure of an element, energy dissipation during the damage process can be derived and it needs to be compared with fracture energy at each case. Therefore, when the dissipated energy reaches the fracture energy, the element can be graphically removed and the fracture process can be simulated. The fracture energy values used in the FE analysis are shown in the Table 4.

Fracture energy	Longitudinal		Transverse	
	Tension	Compression	Tension	Compression
[kJ/m ²]	91.6	79.9	0.22	1.1

Table 4 Fracture energy of composites at each fracture mode [17].

4 DESIGN OF RING BURST TEST DEVICE

The ring burst test device is designed based on the dimension of the composite ring specimen. As can be seen in Fig. 1, the ring burst test system was composed of the vertical column, the segment and the bottom plate. Based on this specimen geometry and the contact angle between the column bar and the segment, the design of a ring burst model was determined.

4.1 Decision of contact angle

Segment-type ring burst test device uses the vertical column and the segment to transfer pressure loads to the specimen. The contact angle (α) between them determines the load transfer ratio and the required maximum displacement of the vertical column. Therefore, it is important to determine the optimized contact angle in designing the ring burst test device. The load transfer ratio from F_1 to F_2 according to the contact angle and the coefficient of kinetic friction can be determined by the equation (1) and be seen in the Fig. 2. The coefficient of kinetic friction was divided into three cases such as non-friction ($\mu = 0$), lubrication ($\mu = 0.1$) and non-lubrication condition ($\mu = 0.3$). it shows that the larger the contact angle and the coefficient of kinetic friction, the lower the transmitted relative load F_2 .

Fig. 2 Load transfer ratio at different coefficient of kinetic friction.

In this relation, the contact angle was determined to be 6° in consideration of the load relation transmitted through the vertical column to the segment. In this case, It is assumed that the composite ring specimen has a fracture strain under 5% along fiber direction and the length of the bottom plate is designed to be under 50cm. Furthermore, when the contact angle is 6° in the lubrication condition, the transmitted load F_2 is about 5 times higher than the applied load F_1 .

4.2 Decision of the number of segments

Unlike a conventional hydro-burst test, when segments are used as a load transfer tool, a gap between segments cause an uneven pressure distribution along the radial direction. Therefore, the specimen will have a non-uniform stress and strain distribution in hoop direction which can lead to unexpected early failure of the specimen during the ring burst test.

The FEA was conducted to confirm the stress distribution of the specimen according to the number of segments in 3D. The number of segments was divided into 3 cases such as 4, 12, and 24 segments and the stress distribution along the hoop direction were measured and compared.

4.3 Usage of the PTFE sheet

Segment-type ring burst test device applies pressure using multiple segments which may result in a non-uniform pressure distribution along the radial direction. This may cause local stress concentration in the specimen during the ring burst test and leads to an unpredictable fracture. Therefore, this makes it difficult to measure the exact failure property of the ring specimen. In addition, Uneven pressure distribution can be occurred due to irregularities of the metal surface that can be generated during the processing of the segment and the vertical column. To prevent those problems, PTFE sheets were used between the segment and the ring specimen. In order to confirm the stress variation of the specimen and the influence of the thickness when using PTFE sheets, FEA was conducted.

5 RING BURST TEST

5.1 Fabrication of ring specimen

The composite ring specimen were made of 12k T700 carbon fiber and epoxy resin using filament winding equipment. By using this equipment, the target pressure vessel can be manufactured by controlling the fiber tension and resin content in the fiber and the fiber tension was determined to be 1kg in manufacturing. All specimens were fabricated on the same basis and cut in 7 pieces from the center. The dimension of the ring specimen is 150 ϕ in diameter, 12.7mm in width, and 0.5mm in thickness.

5.2 Ring burst test device

Based on the modified design of ring burst test device in Fig. 3, the test device was fabricated using SKD11 steel for the vertical column and the segment, SM45C steel for the bottom plate. To transmit uniform pressure in the radial direction, 1t of the PTFE sheet was used in this test device.

Fig. 3 Schematic diagram of modified ring burst test device.

5.3 Test condition

The ring burst test was conducted using a universal testing machine (Instron 5969). The crosshead speed was set at 7.5 mm/min. To measure the uniformity of strain value of ring specimen along hoop direction, 3 strain gages were attached at 120° intervals. Moreover, to confirm the fracture shape and the strain distribution of the ring specimen, digital image correlation (DIC) method using the high-speed camera (FASTCAM SA5) was utilized to take a high-speed video until specimen fracture as can be seen in Fig. 4. In conclusion, the analysis of the fracture shape and process of the ring specimen was conducted and the strain distribution was measured.

Fig. 4 DIC method for measuring strain distribution of ring specimen during ring burst test.

6 RESULTS AND DISSCUSSION

As shown in Fig. 5, the normalized hoop stress distribution of the theoretical model using the equation of load relation and the numerical results of hydro pressure test show the same value. This demonstrates the reliability of the equation of load relation (1) and the possibility of the derivation of hoop stress and strain of ring specimen in a theoretical way. Moreover, as the number of segments increases, the hoop stress distribution of the ring specimen is closer to that of the hydro-burst results and it is confirmed that the max. error is within 30%, 5% and 2% when the number of segments is 4, 12 and 24, respectively. In order to reduce this stress discrepancy, the PTFE layer was used between segments and the specimen so that uniform pressure can be applied to the specimen. In this case, it was confirmed that the error was within 1%. Therefore, a ring burst test device using 24 segments with a 1t PTFE layer was finally considered.

Fig. 5 Normalized hoop strain distribution in different cases.

In order to verify the reliability of the modified ring burst test device, the strain gage and the high-speed camera were used to measure the strain distribution during the ring burst test. Fig. 6 shows that the strain values are similar at 120 intervals along with the circumferential direction of the ring specimen and the max. error was within 1%. This result shows that the test device transmits an even pressure in the radial direction and a uniform deformation can be derived. Furthermore, Fig. 7 shows the hoop strain value from line 1 to 3 along the axial direction before fracture. The max. error of strain right before fracture (point D) was about 1.1% at line 1 and 2.2% at line 3 based on the strain at line 2. From this result, it has been confirmed that the modified segment-type ring burst test device transfer uniform pressure along the radial direction and there is no large discrepancy of strain along the hoop and axial direction of ring specimen. Moreover, abnormal failure due to local stress concentration wasn't caused compared to the previous model. During the ring burst test, the hoop strain distributions at points A to D are shown in Fig. 8.

Fig. 6 Comparison of hoop strain at 3 different point.

Fig. 7 Comparison of hoop strain along axial direction.

Fig. 8 Hoop strain distribution of ring specimen at points A to D.

As can be seen in Fig. 7, it can be confirmed that the strain gradually increases from line 3 to line 1 during the ring burst test. Therefore, it is predictable that there is an inclination angle on the contact surface between segments and the ring specimen and the fractured time of the ring specimen may be different in the axial direction. In order to verify this phenomenon, the fracture procedure of the ring specimen was measured and analyzed using a high-speed camera.

Fig. 9 Fracture progress of ring specimen using high-speed camera at 100,000 fps.

The fracture procedure of the ring specimen during the ring burst test can be seen in Fig. 9. The total fracture time of the ring specimen was within 0.2 ms and the initial crack occurs at about 0.1 ms from the beginning of the fracture. Regarding the fracture procedure, it was confirmed that the initial fracture occurred at one edge of the ring specimen and then it progresses to the other edge through the axial direction. In addition, it is predictable that the gradual interfacial delamination happened between randomly-separated fiber bundles because of the residual stresses remaining in the fiber bundle right after the fracture. As a factor of this phenomenon, there is a possibility of the existence of an inclination angle between the segment and the ring specimen. Therefore, in order to confirm the strain distribution according to the degree of inclination angle, FE analysis was conducted considering the various inclination angle between the segment and the specimen.

Fig. 10 Error of strain based on the strain at line 2 [%].

Error of strain [%]	Exp.	No inclination	0.5° inclination	1° inclination	2° inclination
Line 1	1.11	0.08	1.36	2.92	5.30
Line 3	-2.22	-0.13	-2.37	-4.13	-6.57

Table 5 The error of strain based on the strain at line 2.

As shown in Fig. 10, There are strain error values based on the strain at line 2 and the exact error values are shown in Table 5. When the inclination angle is larger the discrepancy of strain at line 1 and line 3 is also increase. Comparing the error values with respect to the experimental results, it can be confirmed that the experimental results were similar to the result when the inclination angle is 0.5°. Consequently, it is predictable that if there is the inclination angle during the ring burst test, it was about 0.5°.

To analyze the effect of inclination angle on specimen fracture, finite element analysis using Hashin failure criteria was conducted. The material properties used for the damage initiation criteria and damage evolution law are shown in the Table 3 and Table 4. The longitudinal tensile test of composite specimens was first carried out by finite element analysis to ascertain the accuracy of the result of fracture analysis obtained by using the material properties used in the Hashin failure criteria. As can be seen in Fig. 11 and Table 6, It was confirmed that the difference of fracture strain was within 1% when the longitudinal tensile test was carried out with experiment and FE analysis using the fracture energy in the reference paper [9]. Comparing the ring burst test results, the error of the mean fracture strain is also within 1% in each case. The deviation of the strain from line 1 to 3 is similar to the case where the segment and specimen are inclined at 0.5° in FE results. Therefore, it can be assumed that it would have been inclined by 0.5° in the actual experiment.

Fig. 11 Comparison of fracture strain between experiment and FEA.

Contents		Experiment	FEA	Experiment	FEA	FEA
		Tensile test		Ring burst test		
Inclination angle [°]		-	-	-	0	0.5
Strain [%]	Line 1	2.10	2.12	1.82	1.81	1.83
	Line 2			1.80	1.81	1.80
	Line 3			1.76	1.81	1.76
Average strain [%]				1.79	1.81	1.80

Table 6 Comparison of fracture strain at different cases.

In order to compare the effect of inclination angle on the fracture strain of ring specimen, the stress-strain curve up to fracture of the specimen during the ring burst test was derived. The stress-strain curve at the outer lamina during the ring burst test is shown in Fig. 12. Theoretically, the ring specimen fractures first inside and it propagates to the outside of the specimen. In the non-inclination case, the stress is not degraded but it can be confirmed that when there is an inclination angle, the stress decreases and the stiffness of the material also continuously decreases. As a factor for this phenomenon, it is predictable that if the inclination angle is large, the degradation of the stiffness occurs because the damage has already been initiated and evolved at one corner of the ring specimen. In the case of non-inclination angle and 0.5°, the difference of the fracture stress-strain value is within about 1%. Therefore, it can be assumed that if a strain deviation occurs at an inclination angle within 0.5°, it can be the reliable experimental data as the material property.

Fig. 12 Comparison of stress-strain curve during ring burst test at different inclination angle.

7 CONCLUSIONS

To ensure the reliability of the segment-type ring burst system, a new type of test device was developed by improving the disadvantages of previous test methods. To reduce the stress discrepancy during the ring burst test, usage of 24 segments and PTFE sheets led to the reduction of the hoop stress discrepancy within 1%. This means that uniform radial pressure can be transferred by using the modified ring burst test device.

Moreover, derivation of the equation of load relation and the hoop stress model as a theoretical approach in the ring burst system made it possible to calculate the precise stress and strain value compared to the previous theoretical model because this model considered the composite specimen as a 3D transversely isotropy and thick-walled cylinder.

Through experimental results, it was verified that the applied load was transferred uniformly from the segment to the ring specimen by using this modified segment-type test device. It was available to achieve more reliable material data from the experiment because even if there is an inclination angle within 0.5° , the difference of fracture strength was less than 1% in the FE analysis result.

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